

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Challenging the Normal through *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita*

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ABSTRACT

Women have been taught to hold on, to turn a deaf ear and to dismiss the acts of injustice perpetrated against them. Whether in epics, social norms or behavioural expectations, women have been constructed as the silenced ones, frequently as the ones who have always been oppressed by the dominant or the powerful. However, with the ascension of popular culture, film media and literature, these social expectations have been challenged. This paper examines how the film *Thappad* by Anubhav Sinha and the book *The Liberation of Sita* by Volga have questioned the current understanding of resilience, attributing new meanings to it. Although set in different times, both works question the long-standing idea that a woman must be sacrificed and endure. In *Thappad*, a single slap from the husband was enough to call into question a whole culture's propensity to accept small acts of violence. In *The Liberation of Sita*, Sita takes back her voice, gaining strength and wisdom through interactions with other women who have experienced their own injustices. Utilising feminist revisionist mythology, this paper delves into how ancient stories can be re-told to empower women to the extent that they were previously denied. The essay seeks to analyse why stories in film and literature leave a broader influence on the

audience through media convergence theory. Through trauma theory, the paper considers the individual cost of injury, but reinforces the healing through solidarity and self-determination. Finally, both *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita* are not only artistic works or retellings but also exercises in cultural rewriting. They ask readers and spectators to dream of a world in which women are not determined by their pain, but by their decisions, their dignity.

Keywords: compliance, resistance, resilience, freedom, endurance

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

Women have learned through myth, religion, and the everyday social codes around them that patience is a virtue and that suffering is power. This conditioning has been passed down for ages and is inextricably enmeshed within the cultural imagination. The ideal woman is a source of "sacrifice" in the ancient epic. It showcases the ability to endure pain and suffering with dignity in modern popular culture. However, within the same fabric, women who question, resist, or seek their own self-respect are still deemed as unruly or disruptive in the same culture.

In recent years, literature and film have emerged as potent sites of resisting such normalised patriarchal schemas. They are spaces that represent women's silence, oppression, and resilience, exposing and reinterpreting women's lived experiences. Two works which emerge strongly within this context are Anubhav Sinha's film *Thappad* (2020) and Volga's novel *The Liberation of Sita* (2016). The two works are from very different timelines and genres; one is cinematic and contemporary, and the other mythic and literary. Both works, however, grapple with the same question: how long must a woman endure in the name of love, duty, or one's social respectability?

The film *Thappad* is about Amrita. She is a middle-class housewife whose apparently intact marriage ends after her husband slaps her. The slap causes a reconsideration of her life, her views on marriage, and the deeply held belief that minor disrespect is something a woman must endure for the sake of community. In comparison, Volga spins her retelling and argument with the myth of Sita from the Ramayana. She does so through conversations with the lives of other women, whose lives are infused with silence, pain, and resurrected selves. In doing so, Volga critiques the common narrative that Sita's liberation was to be with Rama, and she frames it as

self-agency and spiritual freedom. Stories of suffering women have been a staple of Indian literature and film for decades, and we also ask for an equally relevant focus on how they endure.

This paper reflects on the two works from a feminist lens that renegotiate cultural expectations about being a woman. Grounded in Judith Butler's theory of gender performativity, bell hooks' critique of patriarchal silence, trauma studies from Cathy Caruth and Judith Herman, and Henry Jenkins' theory of media convergence. The paper explores how these narratives suggest new meanings of freedom, voice, and community. Significant moments in each narrative are examined to show how each woman resists the socially constructed identity of endurance and begins to embrace a more complex, comprehensive understanding of strength.

In each work, *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita*, resilience is reimagined, moving from silent endurance to conscious self-respect to collective empowerment. However, both narratives sharply illuminate the way patriarchal culture normalises violence and self-sacrifice. Each counternarrative reimagines culture through its respective mediums, film and a mythic representation, by potentially inspiring readers/audience toward a reimagining of female identities that recognise the dignity of their lived experiences over submission.

Literature Review

The feminist inquiry of mythology has emerged as one of the most significant literary movements in modern Indian literature. The feminist authors generally rewrite the epics like the Ramayana and Mahabharata to point to how the patriarchal story erased women's agency. Volga's *The Liberation of Sita* was originally written in Telugu and then translated into English. The book imagines Sita's banishment not as a tale of punishment and tragedy, but as one of liberation and self-discovery.

As some scholars have noted, Volga's project "deconstructs the male-centred epic story and gives voice back to women who were denied it" (Joy 17). In a comparative study of Volga and Sarah Joseph, Silpa Joy observes that *The Liberation of Sita* "foregrounds female subjectivity through sisterhood and self-reflection (Joy 23). A publication in the IJFANS journal notes that Volga has not mitigated the suffering of mythological women. However, rather elevated their survival, highlighting how "Volga's retelling reimagines the Ramayana from a text of obedience into a text of resistance" (Subhakara 52). Volga's retelling is another example of what Adrienne Rich termed "re-vision"- "the act of looking back, of seeing with new eyes, of entering an old text with a new critical intent" (Rich 35). From this point of view, *The Liberation*

of Sita may be considered both political and cultural. It recasts Sita's exile as a site of interaction and reparation, whereby she and other ostracised women—Ahalya, Renuka, and Surpanakha—share their respective stories of betrayal, punishment, and freedom. Joy contends that such meetings "form a web of common understanding and collective experience which intrudes upon the concept of womanly virtue as isolated" (Joy 28).

Similar to literary adaptations, Indian cinema has witnessed a slow emergence of films addressing gender discrimination and domestic violence. One film that has garnered increasing attention for its resistance against normalised domestic violence is *Thappad* (2020). In the hands of Anubhav Sinha, the private space becomes a site of invisible, yet systemic violence. In the film, a slap denotes the emotional consequences of patriarchal conditioning in public and personal spheres.

Lakshmi writes of *Thappad*, it is "a cinematic manifesto against the invisibility of domestic abuse" and "an indictment of social pressures to forgive." (Lakshmi 2). She notes that, unlike depicting feminism as violence, *Thappad* demands respect. Other critics also note that the film creates a broader narrative arc that intersects multiple narratives, suggesting that resistance transcends a singular act of rebellion or refusal and becomes part of a collective consciousness. If so, then it displays hooks's idea of "the politics of speaking..." (hooks 29).

Theoretical Framework

This research paper builds its arguments on three theoretical perspectives. Feminism serves as the base for analysing both works. It takes into consideration Judith Butler's concept of gender performativity. It emphasises that gender is not a stable identity but rather a regime of repeated acts. Both Amrita and Sita "undo" the expectations imposed on their roles. Their resistance is performative. bell hooks' idea that patriarchy relies on women's silence to wield power also plays a significant role in the analysis of the characters. In *Thappad*, Amrita's refusal to accept a single slap without an apology embodies what hooks states is "the courage to break the rule of silence" (Feminist Theory 36).

Trauma theory is also an important lens for understanding both works. Cathy Caruth describes traumatic experience as "the unclaimed experience"—an event that disrupts the ability to understand it in the moment but returns in repetition and narration (Caruth 4). In *Thappad*, Amrita's slap becomes that returning trauma; it compels Amrita to engage with her realisation of erasure over many years. Judith Herman's idea that healing takes place through "remembrance and reconnection"

(Herman 175) resonates with Volga's telling of Sita's healing through talking with other women. The act of talking, listening, and witnessing leads to wholeness.

Moreover, media convergence theory brings together the literary and filmic dimensions. According to Henry Jenkins, convergence is defined as "the flow of content across multiple media platforms" (Jenkins 2). Both *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita* exist in a converged cultural context in which feminist stories circulate widely. They circulate through many different forms: movies, books, discussions on social media platforms, and activist movements. Jenkins's concept of participatory culture describes a context in which audiences do not simply consume the moments of a story, but rather 'consume' in ways that allow them to discuss, critique, and share stories, amplifying their impact. The conversations that emerged in the digital realm after the release of *Thappad* and the rediscovery of Volga's book in online reading communities reflect this participatory nature of interacting with *Thappad*, and then later rediscovering the book as a form of liberation.

Analysis: *Thappad*

In *Thappad*, Amrita appears to enjoy life as a wife and homemaker. Her life is filled with routines revolving around her husband, Vikram, his work, and his aspirations. The camera constantly positions Amrita in a domestic space, highlighting spatial confinement and a limited everyday routine. This visual language emulates what Judith Butler calls 'the performative repetition of gendered norms' (Gender Trouble 33). Amrita's identity has largely been shaped by years of performing the ideal wife. She is patient without grumbling about her husband's achievements, supportive and nurturing to him and his family, and self-sacrificing. It is within this well-defined and seemingly predictable life that, in one instant, a slap brings the illusion of ordinary life crashing down.

At a party to celebrate Vikram's professional accomplishment, Vikram, upset after having lost a case, slaps Amrita in front of his family and co-workers. For everyone except Amrita, the slap initially seems insignificant. "It was just a slap," is what people told her, "It happens." "It's just a slap" ultimately becomes the central theme of the film, and how a patriarchal society minimises women's pain and normalises aggression against women. bell hooks reminds us that patriarchy "demands both men and women to accept that male domination is natural (The Will to Change 17). Sinha exposes the cultural appropriation of violence against women. It highlights the notion that violence inflicted by men should be forgiven and forgotten.

Amrita's strength, however, lies in her silence. After she is slapped, Amrita does not yell or hit back. Instead, she retreats, and her quietness makes those around her uneasy. In a social structure that expects women to carry hurt silently, her quiet opposition to resuming her everyday life is a refusal. Her silence is no longer passive; it is what hooks has referred to as "the speech of the unheard," the language of protest that is not aggressive (Talking Back 21).

Amrita moves from silence to verbal expression through the phases Judith Herman writes about in trauma recovery: safety, recollection, and reconnection (Trauma and Recovery 155). The immediate shock protrudes from her. She withdraws into herself and cannot understand why the experience feels extreme to her when others deem it banal. However, she starts the next slow phase of recollecting, which is naming the experience as violence. In the film, Amrita tells her attorney, "I did not ask for much, only respect." On its face, it is a very simple statement, but it is political. In requesting respect, she names what feminists have long claimed: that equality does not mean economic or legal equality, but respect and recognition on an emotional level.

Sinha emphasises this change through space and sound. The house, previously filled with ambient noise, becomes quiet in the wake of the incident. The camera holds on to small gestures of domesticity as evidence of her desire to reclaim normalcy on her own terms. The viewer understands that these are silent moments of what Cathy Caruth terms the belated return of trauma: "the wound that cries out," through memory and repetition (Unclaimed Experience 4). The incident keeps repeating in her head as a revelation and recognition of years of unacknowledged subservience.

The reaction of people around Amrita depicts the acceptance of patriarchy and the normalisation of violence in society. The conversations around her depict the ethics of care through patriarchal assumptions, which lead to self-erasure and compliance with disrespectful behaviour. Amrita realises that endurance is not a virtue but compliance when she meets her lawyer and her neighbour, Shivani. This transforms *Thappad* into a collective narrative. The subplots are rooted in the individual dialogues of Sunita, Shivani and Swati. Sunita is physically abused; Swati hides her resentment towards her disrespectful partner, and Shivani is an independent woman. Together, they challenge the silent endurance and suggest that resilience is not about endurance; it is about awareness. The final sequence, the finalisation of her divorce, demonstrates the affirmation of her identity and dignity. Her resistance to compliance highlights Butler's notion of "the re-signification of gender," which means

self-consciously reframing herself in and against socially constructed behaviours (Undoing Gender 41).

Sinha avoids melodrama in his work. Instead, he raises discomfort in the audience. The realism in the film invites introspection over judgement. This is depicted when Vikram apologises to Amrita, and her reaction to the apology is poised and dignified. It signifies that accountability must be a part of the process of forgiveness. The film does not end on a bitter note, but rather on an empowering one. Amrita chooses self-respect over social acceptance, reinforcing the notion that one need not be loud to be free. From the perspective of trauma theory, Amrita's noncompliance signifies healing. She transforms her silence into expression and affliction into intent. Amrita redefines resilience as conscious rejection. This shift is subversive in reclaiming one's dignity as a central part of feminist ethics. *Thappad* is about acknowledgement, resistance and reclaiming of one's own identity. It intricately performs a cultural intervention by reminding us that patriarchy lives on through our ignorance and normalisation of unjust acts in the name of duty, love and relationships.

Analysis: *The Liberation of Sita*

Volga's *The Liberation of Sita* (2016) re-frames one of India's most popular mythological figures within a firmly feminist framework. The novel differs from the typical reimagining of the Ramayana, which highlights Sita's purity, obedience, and patience. The narrative includes the perspectives of other prominent but marginalised characters of Ramayana. It includes Renuka, Ahalya, Surpnakha and Urmila. The narrative connotes a moment of epiphany which leads to Sita's transformation from suffering to self-reclamation.

Volga does not abandon the myth; rather, it changes it. The form she uses is the same as in the Ramayana, allowing readers to see its cultural authority. However, she rewrites the myth on her own terms. Adrienne Rich's concept of "re-vision" - "the act of looking back, of seeing with fresh eyes" (Rich 35) - is very close to being applicable here. Volga's Sita not only "looks back" at her own life but also at the lives of other women, who were never given a voice. A silence that the patriarchy has imposed. She realises that to live in ignorance while you suffer is not really a virtue. Rather, it is betraying yourself. While she was speaking with Ahalya, Sita got her first lesson of awakening. Ahalya, a woman who had been considered disloyal to her husband and had been turned into a stone by him as a result of the curse. Ahalya, who is no longer in need of men's salvation, reveals, "I do not need forgiveness from anyone anymore." This change in Ahalya prompts Volga to question the morality that

takes women's suffering resulting from pure chastity for granted. The curse of myth becomes a metaphor for patriarchal punishment, which, by nature, immobilises female transgressions. When Sita hears what Ahalya has to say, she begins to see silence, and silence is not holy; it is controlled. The meeting and conversation with Ahalya ignite Sita's process of unlearning. Her interaction with Surpanakha advances her exploration. Surpanakha was subjected to vilification when she expressed her desire. However, in Volga's *The Liberation of Sita*, she has been given a voice. She accepts her desire unapologetically. Surpanakha narrates the story of her humiliation. In an act of love, she had her nose cut off. Instead of a tragedy, Surpanakha attains absolute freedom from the delusion of love. "They mutilated my face," she says to Sita, "but they could not touch my spirit." In this instance, Volga dismantles the patriarchal myth that female desire is something to be ashamed of. By listening to Surpanakha, Sita understands that the body is not something to be vilified; it is powerful. The sisterhood that develops between them marks a redefinition of resilience, no longer endurance of suffering but a voice of independent subjectivity.

One of the most significant interactions is with Renuka, who was decapitated by her husband, Jamadagni, in the mythological narrative. In this account, however, Renuka survives and starts her life over by educating the local village women on art and pottery. She says to Sita, "I have learned to shape the clay, and in shaping the clay, I shape myself". She is creating a framework to heal through her labour, agency, and community. Her power is not in forgiving her aggressor or abuser, but in liberating trauma into agency. Herman states, "the process of recovery can occur only in the context of a relationship" (Herman 133). She establishes a social context for women, in which they work together to embody a community that heals among them, an experience of sisterhood similar to Herman's community experience of 'therapy'.

Through these encounters, Sita's perception of duty and devotion also shifts. When she ultimately reflects on her life of trial by fire, exile, and rejection, she realises that the loyalty she had given to Rama had become a kind of imprisonment. Her emancipation, then, is not in reunion but in release. Referring to these events in Volga's book, Sita tells Rama: "You cannot define my truth any longer," indicating her moral and emotional freedom. This declaration re-establishes voice as the foundation of freedom. Volga's engagement with dialogue is intentional and dialogic in the Bakhtinian sense. The voice, or voices, in the novel have significance not only for Sita but for generations of women who have been silenced. In this respect, dialogue replaces the patriarchal monologue of the epic and engenders ongoing feminist dialogue. This is what bell hooks describes as "the communal act of speaking

together," where language becomes a mode of solidarity (Talking Back 44). Unlike the isolation perpetuated by the myth of exile, Volga's narrative constructs a shared space of understanding between women's experiences.

In a thematic sense, *The Liberation of Sita* is connected to trauma theory because each woman's story includes a moment of violation, followed by a reflective period and a process of re-creation. This manner of writing stimulates Cathy Caruth's definition of trauma as an "unclaimed experience" that is called for as a retelling (Caruth 4). By narrating their trauma, these women reclaim their ownership of their pain. In some way, "telling" reconstructs memory into agency. For Sita, that claim of her own experience occurs in its last act of departure. She no longer needs verification from any man, beast, or anything. Volga meditates on spirituality as awareness or consciousness, grounded in either experience or compassion. Sita's moment of enlightenment does not distance her from her body or the context; it actually deepens the connection to the experiences of other women. This awareness is directed toward some orientation, whether it is collective consciousness or feminist ethics. Finally, *The Liberation of Sita* turns one of the most venerable emblems of feminine morality into a potent representation of self-awareness. Volga unearths a historical silence in Sita and has given mythic women a voice in the contemporary world. The writing invites us to consider how personal tales mould women. Sita comes to realise during her journey that freedom does not begin when suffering stops; rather, it begins when we rediscover meaning.

Comparative Analysis

Analysing *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita* together shows a comparative narrative impulse; both texts attempt to subvert the normalisation of women's suffering and to reframe resilience not as suffering but as dignity, not as endurance but as consciousness. Although they are vastly different texts situated in different contexts and modes, one modern and urban, the other mythically and symbolically, both narratives observe a woman turning from silence to speech, from obedient resignation to awareness.

Resistance is the focal point of both narratives, as Judith Butler says, "the politics of performative subversion" (Undoing Gender 42). Women in both narratives break away from the idealised role. Their defiance is not to be read as a dramatic rejection, but rather an assertion of self, a re-performance of gender that rejects victimhood. In patriarchal narratives, the term resilience is often understood as the ability to endure, persevere, and even embrace hardship with grace. Both Volga and

Sinha challenge this view. For Amrita and Sita, resilience is not merely passive but the act of deliberate self-respect. When Amrita departs her marriage, she is not asking to remain in love, but she is choosing respect. When Sita departs from Rama, she is not rejecting her dharma of duty; she is reframing her dharma of self-awareness as a matter of respect. For both, dignity replaces endurance at the epicentre of femininity.

bell hooks's concept of "the politics of love and respect" (All About Love 87) becomes significant here. Hooks illustrates that love without respect is love that is about domination. Both women, by refusing to remain silent, imply that, for love to be normative, it must be grounded in equality. Their refusals become a form of emotional justice.

In both texts, trauma operates as revelation. In *Thappad*, the slap ignites Amrita's awareness of the violence she cannot see, the emotional disenfranchisement and silence of years of expectation. In *The Liberation of Sita*, Sita's exile and the experience of other women reveal thousands of years of cultural and mythic trauma. Cathy Caruth describes trauma as something that "demands retelling" (Unclaimed Experience 5), which applies to both narratives. The stories turn pain into storytelling and trauma into meaning through memory and the ability to articulate it.

Judith Herman's framework of reconnection also resonates. Both Amrita and Sita find healing through connection and not isolation. The world of Amrita expands as she engages with women like Shivani and Sunita, and they discuss injustices and trauma. When Sita meets with other women, they share their experiences and perspectives, creating a sense of sisterhood.

By the terms of Henry Jenkins's convergence theory, *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita* could be viewed as two formations on a continuum of feminist cultural production. Jenkins uses the term convergence to refer to "the flow of content across multiple media platforms, with the active involvement of the audience" (Convergence Culture 2). Both the film and the book encourage audiences to participate and carry on conversations about their particular stories. For example, after *Thappad* was released, audiences carried the conversation into additional public spaces online, book clubs, classrooms, and with activists. The film's creators publicly facilitated the #ThappadDiscussion. They invited the audience to dive deeper into the discourse the film sparked, specifically domestic boundaries and gendered expectations. Similarly, *The Liberation of Sita* generated a renewed interest in feminist myth-making and in the retelling of epics in general, rather than just in the specific myth of Sita that the book addresses. The participatory feature of the sharing conveys

how feminist thought extends across generations and media. Altogether, *Thappad* and *The Liberation of Sita* imply participation in participation cultures, as Jenkins defines them. Participatory cultures are cultures of audience engagement with the invariance of content consumption.

What also unites them is tone. Neither Sinha nor Volga expresses their thoughts with bitterness or revenge. Their protagonists opt for clarity rather than chaos. This appearing sameness, rather than being categorically a lack of strength, represents what Butler has dubbed "the ethical power of non-conformity" (*Undoing Gender* 45). They acknowledge that there are other modes of power beyond being loud; sometimes, power looks like quiet conviction.

Thappad and *The Liberation of Sita* centre on the enduring feminist dimensions of mythic and modern realities, in which the mythic Sita and the contemporary Amrita ultimately reflect one another. The comparison between their paths reveals that patriarchal reasoning has existed in practice for several centuries, and it continues to manifest as a reality for gender relations today. At the same time, a continuity of resistance exists too. Women reconstruct narratives of endurance into ones of self-awareness. The two works together create a continuity of feminist resistance, while encouraging their audience and readership to question what constitutes resilience.

Conclusion

Thappad and *The Liberation of Sita* are both acts of cultural rewriting. They tell stories of women who resist, but they also break down the very notion of what it is "normal" for women to endure. Through different media, film and literature, Anubhav Sinha and Volga present stories that demand that silence be replaced by speech, and that endurance yield to consciousness. For Amrita and Sita, there is no rebellious act of resistance; they stop complying with the norms of ideal women. Both stories, ultimately, hold that resilience is not a testament to the altruistic ability to endure, but as a demonstration of the courage to acknowledge injustice and respond with dignity. Both Sita and Amrita come to recognise that endurance, as a worthy virtue, contributes to the ongoing structure of patriarchy. In their decision to disengage, they do not abandon their worlds but redefine them. This redefinition is the hallmark of feminist ethics; regardless of the volume of one's voice, all voices possess moral weight.

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